

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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with the support of SALGA - South African Local Government Association

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November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in South Africa is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

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Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in South Africa: An Introduction

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South Africa has a uniform system of public finance for local government. The framework for local government finance (revenue-raising, expenditure of revenue and financial management) is provided for by the Constitution. The Local Government: Municipal Finance Management Act of 2003 (MFMA) is the main piece of legislation that gives effect to this framework. There are also several other pieces of legislation that have been enacted to implement the constitutional framework on municipal finance. This section provides an overview of the sources of revenue for municipalities and the expenditure of revenue.

Taxing Powers

Section 229(1) of the Constitution empowers municipalities to impose property rates and user charges on fees for services provided. In addition, the Constitution permits the national government to decentralise other taxes, levies and duties with the exception of income tax, value-added tax, general sales tax and customs duty. The Municipal Property Rates Act of 2004 and the Municipal Fiscal Powers and Functions Act of 2007 have been enacted to give effect to the municipal fiscal powers. The latter introduces additional revenue streams for municipalities. In practice, the exploitation of taxing powers varies within and across categories of municipalities. However, a big difference exists between urban and rural municipalities. Urban municipalities, particularly metropolitan municipalities, get most of their revenue from property rates and surcharges on fees for services. Metropolitan municipalities raise about 75 per cent of their budget from their own sources, thus are largely self-financing. On the other hand, rural municipalities, which are often poor, rely heavily on intergovernmental grants for operations. As a sector, local government raises 70 per cent of its own revenue,⁷² which is high in comparison to local governments in the region.

Intergovernmental Grants

Various forms of intergovernmental grants complement municipalities' own sources of revenue. Section 214(1)(a) of the Constitution provides for the equitable sharing of revenue raised nationally among the national, provincial and local spheres of government in each financial year. The allocation takes place through an annual enactment which determines the share of each sphere, provincial government and municipality – the Division of Revenue Act (DORA). The DORA may only be enacted after organised local government (which is the South African Local Government Association - SALGA) and the Finance and Fiscal Commission (FFC)

⁷² National Treasury, 'Municipal Budget Circular for the 2019/20 MTREF' (MFMA Circular no 94, Municipal Finance Management Act No 56 of 2003, May 2019) 3.

have been consulted and any recommendations of the latter considered. The equitable share is an unconditional grant designed to enable every municipality to provide basic services and perform its constitutional and legislative mandates in its area (Section 227(1)(a) of the Constitution). Its allocation is based on an objective formula that takes into account factors such as population, fiscal capacity and disparities. In addition, metropolitan municipalities also get a share of the general fuel levy as an unconditional grant. Besides these unconditional grants, there are various forms of conditional grants that are allocated to municipalities. Such '[c]onditional grant funding targets delivery of national government's service delivery priorities' in areas such as infrastructure development.⁷³

Borrowing

Section 230A of the Constitution permits municipalities to borrow money to finance current and capital expenditure. Borrowing to finance current expenditure is however restricted for bridging purposes during a fiscal year. These borrowing powers can only be exercised in accordance with national legislation, which is the MFMA. When borrowing money, the Constitution states that a municipal council binds itself and future councils in the exercise of securing loans or investments for the relevant municipality. Section 218(1) of the Constitution provides that the 'national government, a provincial government or a municipality may guarantee a loan only if the guarantee complies with any conditions set out in national legislation'. In practice, the national and provincial governments are reluctant to guarantee municipal loans. As a result, municipal borrowing largely depends on the creditworthiness of a municipality, which is often determined by the private sector actors. When municipalities borrow from the private sector, they often render their assets and revenue streams as surety. This means that high category municipalities, such as metropolitan municipalities, which tend to have a variety of assets and high fiscal capacity, often exercise borrowing powers relative to poor and often rural municipalities because of their financial position.

Expenditure of Revenue

In general, municipalities have the discretion to spend their own revenue and non-conditional grants. There are, however, rules on how municipalities should spend certain funds. For instance, as stated above, the equitable share is there to finance the delivery of basic services to the poor. Municipalities are also required to budget sufficiently for operating expenditure to avoid having a deficit. The repairs and maintenance budget in each financial year should be at least 8 per cent of the value of property, plant and equipment. The consequence of non-compliance with some of the spending requirements can be severe. The national treasury can, for instance, suspend the transfer of intergovernmental grants to the relevant municipality.⁷⁴

⁷³ *ibid* 4.

⁷⁴ See Sec 216(2) of the Constitution.

Municipal officials, who have key responsibilities in budget formulation and implementation, can also be held individually liable for non-compliance.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996

Municipal Finance Management Act 56 of 2003

Municipal Property Rates Act 6 of 2004

Municipal Fiscal Powers and Functions Act 12 of 2007

National Treasury, 'Municipal Budget Circular for the 2019/20 MTREF' (MFMA Circular no 94, Municipal Finance Management Act No 56 of 2003, May 2019)

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This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

